

Comparison of the Predicted Structures of Aggregation Factors in Lactic Acid Bacteria

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The phenomenon of bacterial autoaggregation is widespread among bacteria and has a highly diverse biochemical nature. There is a group of aggregation factors in lactic acid bacteria that have several distinctive features: these are large proteins with a molecular mass greater than 150 kDa, containing an N-terminal signal sequence and an LPXTG-like cell wall anchor domain, as well as a large number of repetitive domains. These aggregation promoting proteins are also called Snow-flake Forming Collagen Binding Aggregation Factors due to their unique aggregation phenotype. Predictions (predicted by the InterPro program) for different members of this group indicate a varying number and, in some cases, different compositions of repetitive domains¹⁻⁵

Comparison of the predicted structures of known aggregation factors (AggL, encoded by the *aggL* gene on a plasmid from *Lactococcus lactis*; AggE, encoded on a plasmid from *Enterococcus faecium*; AggLb, encoded on a plasmid from *Lactobacillus paracasei*; AggLr, encoded by the chromosomally located gene of *Lactococcus raffinolactis*; and AggA, encoded in the chromosome of *Tetragenococcus halophilus*) using AlphaFold2 revealed structural similarities, despite the low level of identity in the primary amino acid sequence (below 40% in some cases). We demonstrate that the structural similarity is primarily due to the repetitive domains. Additionally, all aggregation factors of this type contain an N-terminal signal sequence (predicted by the SignalP - 5.0 program), with the primary sequence of the N-terminus differing among all representatives of this group; however, structurally, they all feature an alpha-helix followed by a predicted cleavage site.

Overall, this study provides greater clarity in understanding the architecture of aggregation factors in lactic acid bacteria.

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